

H2020 - Research and Innovation Action

APPLICATE

**Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: Modelling, observing
system design and Linkages associated with a Changing Arctic
climaTE**

Grant Agreement No: 727862

Deliverable No. D.5

**Launch of a web portal providing an overview of the
project data catalogue**

Submission of Deliverable

Work Package	WP6 Data and HPC Management		
Deliverable No	6.5		
Deliverable title	Launch of a web portal providing an overview of the project data catalogue		
Version	1		
Status	Draft		
Dissemination level	PU - Public		
Lead Beneficiary	1 - AWI		
Contributors	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI	<input type="checkbox"/> 2 – BSC	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 - ECMWF
	<input type="checkbox"/> 4 – UiB	<input type="checkbox"/> 5 – UNI Research	<input type="checkbox"/> 6 – MET Norway
	<input type="checkbox"/> 7 – Met Office	<input type="checkbox"/> 8 – UCL	<input type="checkbox"/> 9 - UREAD
	<input type="checkbox"/> 10 – SU	<input type="checkbox"/> 11 – CNRS-GAME	<input type="checkbox"/> 12 - CERFACS
	<input type="checkbox"/> 13 – AP	<input type="checkbox"/> 14 – UiT	<input type="checkbox"/> 15 - IORAS
	<input type="checkbox"/> 16 - MGO		
Due Date	11/01/18		
Delivery Date	11/30/18		
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 727862.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The APPLICATE Data Portal is a web site enabling humans to interact with the web services powering the APPLICATE Data Management. The Data Portal website has been operating for some time and is now updated with new software and look. The website provides guidance material as well as human/machine interfaces when working with data.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background and objectives

The purpose of this report is to describe the APPLICATE Data Portal. The APPLICATE Data Portal provides a human interface to the APPLICATE Catalogue enabling internal and external users of APPLICATE data to find and access relevant information.

1.2. Organisation of this report

This report merely refers to the online material available in the APPLICATE Data Portal. This is not a scientific report as such, but a description of a user interface. Thus the relation of the human interface to the backend services is briefly described and examples of interfaces are provided.

2. APPROACH

The APPLICATE Data Portal is built using the Open Source Content Management System (CMS) [Drupal](#). This is a widely used CMS that is very flexible and allows integration of a number of services. Drupal was selected as the preferred CMS for integration prior to the initiation of APPLICATE and the decision was based the following requirements:

1. Open Source
2. Broad user base
3. Good availability of standard functionality that could be reused if necessary
4. Flexible

The decision was made through a thorough evaluation and communication with relevant partners in Europe and US. Following this the relevant web services developed around the catalogue (D6.2) was integrated in the CMS solution chosen. The CMS is used to create forms etc requesting information from the user and to wrap and forward this to the backend services which performs the actions required (e.g. search for specific data) and returns the results to the CMS. Within the CMS results are prepared for presentation according to the specifications of the CMS. The module for integration of services with Drupal is available at [GitHub](#).

The APPLICATE Data Portal is available at <https://applicate.met.no/>.

3. SCREENSHOTS

The default page of the APPLICATE Data Portal is shown in Figure 1. This shows a list of all messages and updates that have been posted in the Data Portal. It follows the graphical appearance of the central APPLICATE web page within the constraints of the different CMS solutions used for these two systems. The user navigates the site using the navigation bar which is located below the logo. Registered (and authenticated) users can comment on posted news. In the navigation bar there is a brief introduction to the APPLICATE Data Portal and more dedicated sections with information or tools for the users.

Figure 2 shows the list of information and services provided to the internal and external users of APPLICATE. A dedicated post processing environment which has a number of tools has been set up for APPLICATE internal users. Information on how to register and use this is provided in the support menu along with information on basic data management concepts like metadata and how to encode data for publication and sharing. In order to facilitate the interaction between users and the Data Portal team an issue tracker and a contact form is available. In order to support users that want to submit data a conformance checker for the file format used in APPLICATE ([NetCDF/CF](#)) is available.

FFigure 3 shows the menu where users can search for data. Embedded in this menu are maps showing the YOYP observations. There is one map for the southern hemisphere and one for the northern. FFigure 4 shows the map for the Arctic.

FFigure 5 shows the search interface that users can use to search for data. This has the usual possibilities to search for data by spatio-temporal characteristics. It also allows users to search on parameter keywords (primarily GCMD Science Keywords), owner institution for the data and principal investigator. The spatial bounding box for a search can be chosen using the map and then fin tuned in the text interface.

Figure 1: The default page of the APPLICATE Data Portal is a page where all new messages are listed.

Figure 2: The navigation item for support contains information on several data management services.

Figure 6 shows the results tabulation for the search results. This is provided in a very condensed form where e.g. gridded data are indicated by a thumbnail if they are served through OGC WMS. The user can select to add datasets to the basket through the first column or to launch services on top of the data using the buttons that are available in the dataset name column. Available services currently include

- visualisation of the full discovery metadata,
- visualisation of gridded data using OGC WMS if available,
- visualisation of timeseries at stations if OPeNDAP is available for the data,
- transformation of the data if OPeNDAP is available.

By transformation is here meant e.g. subsetting (selecting parameters, temporal or spatial extent), reprojecting (changing map projection) and in the future changing file formats. The user can also add products to the basket where joint operations on multiple datasets can be undertaken. In order to use these services, users must be registered.

The basket interface is shown in Figure 7. This interface is yet not fully functional regarding all degrees of freedom that can be encountered, but allows visualisation of multiple gridded products, transformation of these (partly), bundling of non serviceable data (e.g. from FTP or HTTP) to archive files (TAR) etc.

Figure 3: Search for data.

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Figure 4: YOPP observations in the Arctic.

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Figure 5: The Data Search Interface.

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APPLICATE

APPLICATE HOME PAGE DATA PORTAL NEWS ABOUT SUPPORT AVAILABLE DATASETS LOGIN

Home / Search results

Number of datasets found: 456

Search results

Dataset name	Institutions	Abstract	Collection period
<input type="checkbox"/> YOPP (Year Of Polar Prediction) Metadata	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts	Enable a significant improvement in environmental prediction capabilities for the polar regions and beyond, by coordinating a period of intensive observing, modelling, verification, user-engagement and education activities. The Year of Polar Prediction (YOPP) is one of the key elements of the Polar Prediction Project. YOPP is scheduled to take place from mid-2017 to mid-2019.	2017-05-01T12:00:00Z to 2019-05-31T12:00:00Z
<input type="checkbox"/> met-arome-arctic-2p5km-extracted Download data Metadata Transform	Norwegian Meteorological Institute	Extracted variables based on the latest run of the AROME-Arctic model, without additional post-processing. Data on surface, and selected model and pressure levels. Horizontal data resolution is 2.5km. The forecast is updated 4 times per day. For historical runs see http://thredds.met.no/thredds/catalog/aromearcticraw/catalog.html	2016-02-01T12:00:00Z to

Figure 6: Tabulation of search results.

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Figure 7: The basket interface.

4. SUMMARY

The APPLICATE Data Portal is up and running and has been so for quite some time. The most recent update of the human interface was done in November 2018. The next update is scheduled for spring 2019.

5. REFERENCES

APPLICATE D6.2 – Data catalogue and services.